

INTEGRATION OF DISCIPLINES IN THE TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'limni takomillashtirishda fanlararo integratsiyaning ahamiyati haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida texnologik ta'lim fanlarini integratsiyalash masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: integratsiya, kasbiy va shaxsiy rivojlanish, fanlararo integratsiya

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о важности междисциплинарной интеграции в улучшении образования. Рассмотрены вопросы интеграции предметов технологического образования в педагогических вузах.

Ключевые слова: интеграция, профессиональное и личностное развитие, междисциплинарная интеграция

Abstract: This article provides information on the importance of interdisciplinary integration in improving education. The issues of integration of technological education subjects in pedagogical universities are considered.

Key words: integration, professional and personal development, interdisciplinary integration

Today, there is a growing need for personnel who can quickly and competently navigate the constantly changing demands of society. Therefore, in modern educational institutions, education is aimed at developing the training of competitive, competent specialists in accordance with the requirements of the economy and labor market.

One of the most important methodological foundations of science, along with the use of modern technologies in preparing students, promotes interdisciplinary integration as a necessary educational process.

Integration is the unification, interpenetration, synthesis of sciences and scientific disciplines, combining them into a single whole. Integration is one of the most actively developing features of various spheres and processes of the modern world.

The introduction of interdisciplinary integration is associated with an increase in the volume of academic subjects, which in no way affects the decrease in knowledge acquired by the student and personal development.

This helps to form a holistic worldview of students and preserve a creative, emotional and value-based culture of thinking.

Integration eliminates repetition of topics, saves time, and provides a complete and clear explanation of the main or additional phenomena and processes presented in given topics in different disciplines. Therefore, an important task in the educational field of "Technology" is the organization of a set of educational disciplines that ensures the achievement of personal, scientific and interdisciplinary educational results.

The connection between academic subjects is one of the most important

fundamental requirements of modern didactics.

It is possible to show the integration of the discipline of training bachelor students in the direction of “Technological Education”:

1. Electrical engineering, electronics and electric drives and alternative energy sources;
2. Robotics and mechatronics;
3. Food processing and basic home economics and others.

In the integration of some disciplines, the regional and national aspects can be taken into account. The culture of each nation has a beneficial effect on the spiritual and moral formation and development of the personality of students.

Discipline integration reduces the number of subjects that students have to study and allows them to have a clear understanding of the same topic or phenomenon.

Despite the undeniable effectiveness of using integration between various academic disciplines and courses being studied, the university teacher himself intuitively determines the extent of its reasonable application in a specifically chosen lesson¹.

In conclusion, in the field of technology education, the scope of training for students in vocational and technical sciences should cover a wide range of subjects. When reducing the volume of subjects studied through integration, it is necessary to take into account the technical, professional orientation and national craft.

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